

The impact of Nina Thornhill on students at UCL

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Abstract: John Mitchell is Vice-Dean Education in the Faculty of Engineering Sciences at University College London (UCL). From 1993 to 1996 he was a student on the B.Eng. programme in the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering and was taught and tutored by Nina Thornhill.

Keywords: University College London, education, electronic and electrical engineering, tutor.

In 1993 I, along with about 90 other fresh-faced undergraduates, joined the Department of Electric and Electrical Engineering at UCL. The cohort where one of the first years to see changes in teaching which included a revision of the topics in the first year, mathematics taught within the department and an expansion of the MEng cohort. As with all intakes we quickly sized up and characterised the staff. Nina's commitment to the teaching of the department stood out immediately. Firm, but also generous in her willingness to explain. Part way through my time at UCL I had the pleasure of being tutored by Nina as my own personal tutor took a sabbatical. Up until that point practical electronics had been a joy but the more abstract areas, electromagnetics in particular, had remained something of a mystery. I still vividly remember being part of a small group in Nina's office and for the first time being able to relate the mathematics to something tangible – something that I could

conceptualise and understand. To me this is the mark of a great teacher and something that has remained with me.

Later I joined the staff of the Department and by now Nina was head of teaching. During this time the department benefited greatly from her leadership. The emphasis on process was always clear, something I have no doubt came from her chemical engineering training. Again, this is something that has stayed with me to this day and I often reflect on her approach in my role as vice-dean. I can't help but observe that clear processes, pragmatically operated are central to a good student experience.

The impact of her leadership in teaching within the Department is still being felt today and is something that the department is much richer for. I'm sure all my colleagues as well as all the former students that have passed through her tutorials and classes here will wish her a long and fruitful retirement.